

An innovative compression-dominant structural system for carbon-negative buildings: An overview of EIC Pathfinder project ‘CARBCOMN’

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Abstract

The CARBCOMN project proposes a compression-dominant, carbon-negative structural system enabled by extrusion-based 3DCP and mineral carbonation. This paper presents an overview of early outcomes from the initial experimental validation of the proposed framework. This involves the factorial experimental design used to develop formulations composed solely of stainless steel slag derivatives and the first 3D-printing tests. Mix M-0.5_0.25 (a/b = 0.5, w/b = 0.25) achieved the highest compressive strength after carbonation curing at 3% $\overline{\text{CO}}_2$ concentration, 20 °C temperature, and 60% relative humidity, for 7 days. Preliminary rheological characterization confirmed sufficient yield stress to ensure desired buildability for the proposed trial geometry. The optimum mix was successfully extruded in the 3D-printing trials, maintaining geometric stability during deposition. These findings confirm the feasibility of producing 3D-printable, carbon-negative formulations solely from industrial by-products. The work supports CARBCOMN’s broader objective of enabling circular construction systems through digital fabrication and material innovation.

1 Introduction

The construction industry faces urgent demands to improve sustainability while addressing enduring labour shortages. These challenges are compounded by the sector’s contribution to global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, necessitating a radical rethinking of how buildings are designed, constructed and decommissioned [1]. Current energy-rooted approaches and material-intensive practices are increasingly misaligned with emerging environmental targets, such as the 2050 net-zero emissions. Consequently, a comprehensive upgrade to the sector’s design philosophy and technological framework is both timely and essential [2]-[4]. Among these, alkali-activated materials (AAMs), particularly alkali-activated slags (AAS), have attracted significant attention due to their high early strength, low permeability, and CO₂-reduction potential [5]. However, AAS systems often suffer from drawbacks such as

durability uncertainties, efflorescence, and the need for caustic activators, which limit their large-scale adoption and environmental benefits. Moreover, their handling and health risks pose practical constraints for implementation in automated manufacturing [6].

In parallel, mineral carbonation has emerged as a promising alternative to chemical activation, offering permanent CO₂ sequestration by forming stable carbonate phases in reactive industrial residues. Several studies have demonstrated that carbonation curing can develop sufficient mechanical strength while reducing the need for synthetic activators, especially in slag-rich systems [7].

Structurally, recent work has emphasized compression-dominant geometries, capitalizing on concrete's inherent compressive strength while minimizing reinforcement. This approach aligns well with digital fabrication techniques such as 3D concrete printing (3DCP), enabling optimized geometries inspired by unreinforced masonry. Examples include funicular shell structures, which showcase how computational design and form-active systems can reduce material use [8]-[10].

In this context, the CARBCOMN project— short for ‘CARBon-negative COMpression dominant structures for deconstructable CONcrete buildings’ builds upon these advances by developing carbon-negative concretes from unactivated stainless steel slag derivatives, cured through controlled mineral carbonation. The approach eliminates the need for Portland cement or alkaline activators, offering a safer, scalable, and circular solution. Coupled with robotic 3DCP and compression-only structural logic, CARBCOMN proposes a digitally integrated, deconstructable construction system. This paper presents early experimental validation of this framework, including material performance, rheological characterization, and print trials.

This overview briefly outlines the fundamental concepts and early research methods and outcomes of the CARBCOMN project, with the aim of contributing to a more sustainable automated future in concrete construction.

The early findings presented in this paper form part of the project's commitment to develop carbon-negative mixes using locally sourced by-products and carbonation-curing.

2 Experimental program

2.1 Materials

The binder (Carbinox 0–0.25 mm) and sand (Stinox 0–2 mm) derived from stainless steel slag were provided by Orbix. Polycarboxylate superplasticizer, SP (35% solid content, MasterGlenium 51, by BASF) and a hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, VMA (Tylose MOT 60000 YP4 by ShinEtsu) were used to obtain a stable and printable rheology. Tap water was used in all mixing operations. A factorial experimental design of 2 independent variables (aggregates to binder ratio, a/b and water to binder ratio, w/b) was employed, each evaluated at 3 levels. Levels herein refer to multiple values of the independent variables, combinations of which make the different mixes of the test program. The influence of chemical admixtures was assumed to be limited to rheological modification with no significant contribution to strength development. The mix design is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Mix design for the initial testing program.

Mix	Effective water to binder ratio (w/b)	Fine Aggregate to binder ratio (a/b)	SP dosage (% of binder)	VMA dosage (% of binder)
M-0.5 0.25	0.25	0.5	0.8	0.06
M-0.5 0.30	0.30	0.5	0.3	0.06
M-0.5 0.35	0.30	0.5	0.0	0.08
M-0.7 0.25	0.25	0.7	1.0	0.08
M-0.7 0.30	0.30	0.7	0.5	0.08
M-0.7 0.35	0.35	0.7	0.0	0.05
M-1.0 0.25	0.25	1.0	1.8	0.10
M-1.0 0.30	0.30	1.0	1.0	0.10
M-1.0 0.35	0.35	1.0	0.5	0.10

2.2 Methodology

Material constituents were mixed in a planetary mixer at a maximum rotational speed of 285 rpm for 2.5 minutes. The quantity of mixing water was appropriately adjusted to cater for water absorption capacity (3.1%) of the aggregates. Using additives, the mix rheology was optimized to achieve a flow table value of 150 – 170 mm after 25 drops, in accordance with ASTM 1437-20 [11]. The initial mix design was developed through trial and error, targeting extrudability as the primary evaluation criteria. A 2D drill-driven mortar extruder shown in Fig. 1 was used for extrudability tests and subsequent small-scale sample printing from extrudable mixes. Extrudability was defined as: (1) the ability of a mix to be continuously ejected without breaking the plastic nozzle, and (2) its ability to retain geometric stability with minimal deformation upon layer deposition [12],[13]. Specimens consist of four layers, each of 15 mm height, 45 mm width and 200 mm length, were printed. Specimens were transferred to a carbonation chamber 40 to 60 minutes after printing. Under the scope of this study, carbonation curing was conducted for 7 days under controlled carbonation conditions (CO_2 concentration = 3%, (1 bar), Temperature = 20°C, and relative humidity = 60%). After carbonation curing, the specimens were cut into standard prisms for flexural and compressive strength tests, in accordance with EN 12390-5 [14] and EN 12390-3 [15] respectively. To account for possible anisotropy due to the layer-wise structure, strength measurements were performed by applying the load in two directions, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1 Preparation of small-scale specimens: 2D extrusion of specimens (left), samples in the CO_2 chamber (right).

Fig. 2 Loading sign convention of specimens.

In line with the project's objective to employ compression-dominant geometries, the mix exhibiting the highest compressive strength was selected for the initial block printing trial. The trial-print block was primarily to test the printability of the initial mix. Structural design and optimization of the final blocks for compression dominance is not covered in the scope of this paper. Structural optimisation of the blocks follows principles of unreinforced concrete masonry, translated from the circular economy butterfly diagram (7). To predict the yield stress evolution of the mix, slow penetration tests were performed at room temperature, using a rheometer (Anton-paar, MCR 102). The peak yield stress was used to estimate the critical printing height, serving as a primary check for printability of the mix for the selected block geometry. The critical printing height, H_{cr} was computed from Eq. (1) [16]. The bulk mix was prepared in a 4-minute cycle and subsequently pumped through a flow rate-controlled pump (Rudolf STROBOT 408) of diameter 25.4 mm. The initial blocks were 3D-printed using a 6-axis robotic arm (ABB IRB 6650) shown in Fig. 3 and were carbon-cured separately under the same conditions as the small-scale samples. The 3D-printed blocks were transferred to the carbonation chamber 3 hrs after printing.

$$H_{cr} = \frac{\sqrt{3} \times \tau_0}{\rho_m \times g} \quad (1)$$

Where τ_0 is the yield stress of the mix in Pa, ρ_m is the density of the mix, measured as 1882 kg/m³, and g is acceleration due to gravity, taken as 9.81m/s².

3 Results

From the initial test program, the mix with a/b of 0.5 and w/b of 0.25 exhibited the highest compressive strength (Fig. 4). This performance is attributed to the highly CO₂-reactive binder, which rapidly formed CaCO₃ as the binding phase during carbonation [17].

M-0.5_0.25 was selected for the initial block-scale 3D printing trial. Based on the yield stress measurements from slow penetration tests (Fig. 5), the critical printing height reaches 0.74 m (Eq. (1)), which confirms its ability to support the printing height for the compression-dominant geometry proposed for the trial-print. Blocks were successfully printed and retained geometric stability during deposition as shown in Fig. 6. Carbonation curing under 20% CO₂ is currently ongoing to assess improvements in reaction kinetics and mechanical performance relative to the initial curing at 3% CO₂.

Fig. 3 Robotic arm employed for block printing .

Fig. 4 Mechanical strength results of best performing mix cured at 3% CO₂ concentration: compressive strength (left), flexural strength (right).

Fig. 5 Strength evolution from slow penetration tests: normal penetration force evolution (left), yield stress evolution (right).

Fig. 6 Proposed trial block geometry (left); printed geometry with optimized mix (middle); printed block in CO₂ chamber (right).

4 Conclusion

The project's early results demonstrate the feasibility of producing 3D printable concrete from 100% secondary constituent materials. The optimum mix M-0.5_0.25 ($a/b = 0.5$, $w/b = 0.25$) exhibited high compressive strength (22MPa) after 7 days of carbonation curing at 3% CO₂, 20 °C, and 60% RH, with a printable rheology confirmed in preliminary rheology characterization and 3D-printing trials. The achieved mechanical performance at this stage is desirable for unreinforced concrete masonry structural systems. These results validate the potential of cement-free, CO₂-sequestering formulations for digital fabrication.

However, this paper is limited to findings from material-scale characterization and initial 3D-printing trials. Long-term durability, carbonation kinetics at higher CO₂ concentrations, and mechanical performance of 3D-printed elements remain to be assessed.

As part of a broader technological framework, the project is investigating discrete compression-dominant structural systems and deriving design strategies informed by masonry principles. Durability performance will be evaluated alongside a life cycle cost analysis incorporating quantified economic and environmental indicators. To enable geometry-specific applications, open-source CAD tools and integrated design-to-fabrication (DTF) workflows will be developed, leading to a set of codifiable design principles for structural components and assemblies. The project culminates in the extrusion-based 3D-printing of carbon negative block geometries, with focus on optimizing boundary conditions for efficient assembly.

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